

Table 2. Fungicides not effective against rice red stripe disease.^a CLRRI, Omon, Haugiang, summer-autumn 1990.

Chemical	Dosage (parts/thousand)	Time of application	Disease severity		Unfilled grains/panicle (no.)	Grain yield (t/ha)
			% leaves with disease at 7 DAS	% leaf area covered by disease at 14 DAS		
Kitazin 50 % EC	2	7 DAH	23.23	23.85	38.1	4.4
Hinosan 40 % EC	2.0	7 DAH	22.77	50.07	38.5	4.9
Kasuran 20 % WP	1.5	7 DAH	26.68	51.47	48.4	4.1
Oryzemat 8 % G	4 kg ai/ha	20 DBH	25.78	52.13	33.3	4.6
Control (unsprayed)	-	-	23.36	61.17	41.3	4.4
LSD (0.05)			ns	19.52	ns	ns

^a DAH = days after heading, DAS = days after spraying, DBH = days before heading.

Integrated pest management—insects

A parasitoid of stalk-eyed fly eggs in West Africa

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During ecological investigations on the stalk-eyed fly (SEF) *Diopsis longicornis* Macquart, in 1989 wet season at IITA in southwestern Nigeria, we introduced SEF eggs into an experimental field to explore indigenous parasitoids.

Potted plants of rice cultivar Suakoko 8 carrying 1-d-old eggs from a screenhouse culture of SEF were exposed for 1 d in ricefields each week for 2 mo. Exposed

eggs were incubated in the laboratory in glass vials with a wet wad of cotton.

Three to four trichogrammatid wasps developed from each SEF egg. Upon dissection, each SEF egg showed as many as 8-9 larval/pupal stages of the parasitoids. Superparasitism was 12-15%. The developmental period of the parasitoid was 7-9 d.

The parasitoid was identified as *Trichogramma* sp. near *kalkae* Schulten & Feijen. This species has the distinctive genitalia characteristic of *T. kalkae*, a species found in SEF eggs in Malawi. However, the antennae of *T. sp.* near *kalkae* resemble those of *T. mandelai* Pintureau & Babault, found in eggs of Noctuidae (Lepidoptera) from Chad.

It may be that *T. sp.* near *kalkae* has not yet been described, or that the degree of intraspecific variation in genitalia characters or antennae is great. □

A population of brown planthopper (BPH) biotypes 1 and 2 mixture in Guangdong, China

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Guangdong in South China is the primary area of BPH immigration from Southeast Asia. BPH biotypes 2 and 3 are already present in the Philippines, Indonesia,

Vietnam, and the Solomon Islands. In June 1990, we collected a BPH colony in Gaozhou county, Guangdong, and isolated BPH biotypes 2 and 3.

For biotype evaluation, progenies of these BPH were evaluated using seedling bulk and survival rate tests. IR26 and Mudgo with the *Bph 1* resistance gene, IR36 and ASD7 with *bph 2*, IR56 with *Bph 3*, and TN1 with no resistance gene were used as identifying varieties.

Gravid BPH females were caged on 35-d-old plants of IR26, Mudgo, and ASD7, with 20 replications. First-

generation nymphs were evaluated on IR26, Mudgo, ASD7, and TN1 in the seedling bulk test. If some of the progenies damaged IR26, Mudgo, or ASD7 seedlings, the insects were mass-reared on TN1 for seedling bulk and survival rate tests.

In the seedling bulk tests, each 7-d-old rice seedling in the mass seedbox was infested with 10 newly hatched nymphs. When TN1 seedlings died, responses of all varieties were rated by the *Standard evaluation system for rice scale*. In survival rate tests, 10 third- to fourth-instar nymphs were caged on 35-d-old potted rice plants, with five replications per variety. BPH were counted 10 d after infestation.

Two and one replications of nymphs isolated with IR26 and Mudgo damaged IR26 and Mudgo seedlings, respectively. However, nymphs isolated with ASD7 did not damage IR26, Mudgo, or ASD7.

A progeny from a female isolated on

Damage rating

1. Damage rating to rice varieties infested with Gaozhou BPH colony and SC26 BPH population.

Survival (%)

2. Survival rate of SC26 BPH population. Bars with a common letter are not significantly different by Duncan's multiple range test (P 0.05).

IR26 (SC26), which damaged IR26 and Mudgo, was evaluated in seedling bulk and survival rate tests, with the original Gaozhou BPH colony as control. The varieties responded differently to the populations in the seedling bulk test (Fig. 1). TN1 showed susceptibility to the original Gaozhou BPH, IR26 was moderately resistant, and Mudgo, ASD7, IR36, and IR56 were resistant. TN1, IR26, and Mudgo were susceptible to the newly isolated SC26 population, IR36 was

moderately resistant, and ASD7 and IR56 were resistant. The survival of the SC26 population on varieties differed: survival on IR26 and TN1 was significantly higher than on Mudgo, IR36, ASD7, and IR56 (Fig. 2).

Although BPH biotype 1 was dominant in the Gaozhou colony, some BPH biotype 2 insects were found. IR26 could be damaged by BPH biotype 2; mature Mudgo plants could not. □

Wild rice: a new host for *Hysteronura setariae* (Thomas) [Hemiptera: Aphididae] in the Philippines

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The rusty plum aphid *H. setariae*, a vector of sugarcane and soybean mosaic virus, is a polyphagous pest that occurs year-round in coconut, coffee, and grasses [particularly *Echinochloa* spp., *Leptochloa chinensis* (L.) Nees, and

Eleusine indica (L.) Gaertn.] and occasionally in wheat and rice.

The wingless female is dark brown, shiny, and relatively small (1.70 mm long, 1.00 mm wide), with black antennal segments 1 and 2 and apices of segments 5 and 6, black siphunculi long and cylindrical, cauda white and parallel-sided. The frontal tubercles in the head are absent. The winged form is 1.50 mm long and 0.70 mm wide with a dark brown head and thorax. The forewing has a twice-forked median vein and the hindwing has a cubitus (Fig. 1).

For the last 5 yr, *H. setariae* has invaded wild rices *Oryza minuta* Presley and *O. officinalis* Wall in an IIRRI greenhouse. Aphid density was high (>50 aphids or 2-6 colonies/panicle) during the Jan-Apr dry season, but no yield loss has been reported.

We studied the effect of aphid feeding at different densities on grain development. Each booting tiller was enclosed in a 2.5- × 11-in cylindrical mylar cage with

a nylon mesh vent on top and a sleeve on the side. Aphids were released into cages at six densities, and the sleeve was taped to prevent escape. *H. setariae* were allowed to feed on the panicle for 96 h and then were killed by a pyrethroid insecticide. Percent of damaged grain was determined using the formula

$$\% \text{ damage (adjusted)} = \frac{U(\%) - u(\%)}{100 - u(\%)} \times 100$$

where U is percent unfilled grains in each test and u the percent unfilled grains in the control.

Aphid feeding produced 4-43% empty grains, proportional to pest density (Fig. 2). The relatively low fertility of wild rices, particularly *O. officinalis*, was further reduced by aphid feeding. *O. minuta* and *O. officinalis* appear to have little or moderate resistance to aphids. □

Comparing parasitoid-host responses in laboratory experiments

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Parasitoid-host responses are determined in the laboratory by recording host parasitization at different parasitoid densities. Two components of the functional response are estimated: instantaneous attack rate *a* and a satiation factor, or handling time *T_h*.

One way to obtain these estimates is with nonlinear curve-fitting procedures found in statistical packages such as SAS, BMDP, and MINITAB. While these methods often provide standard errors of the parameter estimates from which comparisons can be made, they generally do not permit comparisons of the curve of total responses.

In a statistical test for significance between two or more functional response curves, two assumptions are inherent: 1) a null hypothesis that the curves represent samples from a common population, and 2) that the best possible sets of parameters describing the model's function can be estimated.

The parasitoid-host functional

1. Winged form of the female *H. setariae*.

2. Correlation of different aphid densities per panicle with damaged grain in wild rices *O. minuta* and *O. officinalis*.